

Research Article

Assessment of Selected Heavy Metals in Sewage Sludge Disposal Soils in Abakaliki, Southeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to assess sewage sludge disposal sites in Abakaliki Southeastern Nigeria for agricultural utilization with respect to selected heavy metals (Sn, Cu, Fe and Zn). Soil samples were collected at 0 -30 cm depth from A - Excreta disposal site, B – Urine disposal site, C – Wastewater disposal site and D – Control (Non-disposal site) and analysed for selected heavy metals (Sn, Cu, Fe and Zn). The data collected was analyzed using standard error of the mean. Results showed higher values of heavy metals in sewage sludge disposal sites than non-disposal site and all the heavy metals observed are within the normal range in soils. Thus, the agricultural utilization of sewage sludge is not limited by heavy metals content of sewage sludge since the values of heavy metals observed in this study are within the normal range in soils.

Key Words: Agriculture, dumpsite, heavy metal, sewage sludge, utilization

1. INTRODUCTION

The disposal of sewage sludge on soils has been a widespread practice in many places in Abakaliki, especially at Ochoudo city where sewage sludge is used as soil amendment to improve soil productivity for crop production. Sewage sludge is a rich source of organic matter and nutrients, so there is a possibility of their broader agricultural utilization. However, agricultural utilization of this material is limited by excessive quantities of heavy metals (Jakubus and Czekala, 2001). Raw sewage contains significant concentrations of heavy metals which are not degraded by the processes of sewage treatment, they leave the sewage treatment works in either the final effluent or the sludges produced (Carrondo *et al.*, 1978). Excessive accumulation of heavy metals in agricultural soils does not only cause soil contamination but also leads to elevated accumulation of heavy metals in plants' tissues and thus have negative effects on food quality and safety (Mbah *et al.*, 2011). There is also the possibility of transfer of these heavy metals to other environmental media such as groundwater, surface water and air. According to McBride (1995), metal transfer from sewage sludge through soil to the ground water represents one of the most critical hazards associated with application of sewage sludge to soils. Heavy metals have been known to act as biological poisons due to their bio-accumulation abilities (Akinola *et al.*, 2011). Their levels are highly concentrated in soils and sediments, which are readily taken up by plant during growth. These metals have detrimental effects upon crop growth and yield. They also have adverse effects in the environment on other living organisms if their disposal and dispersal is not regulated in a manner that prevents the accumulation of these metals to toxic levels. However, when these heavy metals are in free state, they are known to be non-toxic but are dangerous in the cation form when they bind to the soil and is released into the environment thereby causing environmental and health hazards (Bunce, 1990). Dowdy and Volk (1984) reviewed the extensive movement of heavy metals in sewage sludge treated soils and concluded that the movement most likely occurred where disposal of sewage sludge was made on sandy, acidic and low organic matter soils, receiving high rainfall or irrigation water. McBride (1995) noted that heavy metals retention is closely associated with metal-organic complexation and soil pH and that heavy metal in soils tend to accumulate in or very near the surface layers of the soil. The objective of this study is to assess sewage sludge disposal sites for agricultural utilization with respect to the selected heavy metals (Sn, Cu, Fe and Zn).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area: This study was carried out in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Southeastern Nigeria. The area lies at latitude 6° 19' N and longitude 8° 06' E in the derived savannah of the southeast agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. The annual rainfall is 1700 – 1800 mm. The rainfall pattern is bimodal between April – July and September – November with short spell in August while the minimum and maximum temperatures of the area are 27°C and 31°C respectively. The soil belongs to the order Ultisol and is classified as Typic Haplustult (FDALR, 1985).

Field Method: The reconnaissance survey of the study area was carried out and the following sites were selected:

- A – Excreta disposal site
- B – Urine disposal site
- C – Waste water disposal site
- D – Control (Non-disposal site)

Five soil samples were collected from each site at 0 -30 cm depth using auger. These auger soil samples were air-dried, sieved with a 2 mm sieve and used for laboratory determination of selected heavy metals.

Laboratory Determination: 1g of each sample was weighed and digested with a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids. The clear digest was diluted into a flask with distilled water. The sample solutions were analyzed for Tin (Sn), Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe) and Zinc (Zn) using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Alloway, 1996).

Data Analysis: The data collected was analyzed using standard error of the mean (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the result of Sn, Cu, Fe and Zn recorded in each site. Control recorded the lowest Sn value of 3.43mgkg⁻¹. This observed Sn value in control was lower than the Sn values in A, B and C by 566%, 443% and 6%, respectively. The order of Cu increase in sewage sludge disposal site was B>C>A>D. Similarly, control recorded the lowest Fe value of 15.57mgkg⁻¹ while the Fe values in the sewage sludge disposal sites ranged between 19.53mgkg⁻¹ – 33.05mgkg⁻¹ with the highest and lowest values observed in excreta and wastewater disposal sites, respectively. Control also recorded the lowest Zn value of 4.43mgkg⁻¹. This observed value of Zn in control was lower than that of A, B and C by 613%, 90% and 104%, respectively.

Table 1: Heavy metals content of each sites (mgkg⁻¹)

Site	Sn	Cu	Fe	Zn	Normal Range
					in Soil
A	22.84±0.41	10.61±0.18	33.05±0.56	31.60±0.61	Sn = 1 – 2000
B	18.61±0.37	13.23±0.23	20.11±0.32	8.40±0.19	Cu = 2 – 1500
C	5.45± 0.18	12.59±0.26	19.53±0.16	9.05±0.21	Fe = 4 – 2000
D	3.43± 0.13	9.48±0.27	15.57±0.09	4.43± 0.16	Zn = 1 – 900

- *A – Excreta disposal site
- B – Urine disposal site
- C – Wastewater disposal site
- D – Control (Non-disposal site)
- Normal range in soil (Alloway, 1996)

DISCUSSION

The study showed that sewage sludge increased soil heavy metals relative to control. Njoku and Ngene (2012) observed higher heavy metals in an abandoned mechanic site than non-mechanic site. The values of the heavy metals observed in all the studied sites are within the normal range in soils (Alloways, 1996). On the other hand this study is not in agreement with Jakubus and Czekala (2001) who observed that agricultural utilization of this material

is limited by excessive quantities of heavy metals. Similarly, the concentrations of heavy metals observed in this study were lower than the one recorded for oil field soils and automobile spare part soils (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2007).

Similarly, Mbah *et al.* (2011) in their study of accumulation of pollutants in an ultisol amended with burnt and un-burnt rice milled wastes observed that organic wastes such as rice mill wastes at the rate of 10 t ha⁻¹ and 20 t ha⁻¹ could be used as soil amendment on continuous basis since they do not constitute pollution problem. Likewise this study observed that agricultural utilization of sewage sludge is not limited by heavy metals since heavy metals observed in sewage sludge dumpsites were higher than that of non-dumpsite but are within the normal range in the soil.

CONCLUSION

Sewage sludge is a source of soil heavy metals (Sn, Cu, Fe and Zn) as observed from this study. However, heavy metals contributed to soils by sewage sludge cannot limit utilization of sewage sludge in agricultural production as the values of heavy metals recorded in this study are within the normal range in soils.

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